

Why, AI.

BUSTED
MYTH

**AI Models are abstract and do not need
personal data**

MYTH

Chair of Legal Informatics @Saarland University

- **Computer science and law** research group in the Faculty of Law (and, as a secondary membership, the Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science)
 - Also: Association with the CISPA Helmholtz Center for Information Security and Senior Fellow of the German Research Institute for Public Administration
 - Head: Christoph Sorge

- **Interdisciplinary** and international team with backgrounds in law/computer science/related subjects
- Focus areas: Intersection of computer science and law, **Privacy by Design**, Machine learning on legal texts
- Third-party funding in **cooperation** with research institutions, companies, government authorities and public prosecutors

Introduction

- Focus here: Machine learning (main driver of AI progress in recent years)
 - In particular: Supervised machine learning which learns from **training data** and is evaluated using **test data**

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Machine learning models

- Common (implicit) assumption: Even when learning from personal data, the resulting model is an **aggregation/abstraction**, which no longer contains personal data
- Reasoning:
 - **Only statistical information** is required for classification / prediction tasks
 - Machine learning models are typically **smaller** than the training data set
→ **not all information** can be contained in the model
 - **Overfitting** is bad for machine learning performance: We want to learn **patterns** in a type of data – not information about some person in the training data set

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 - De facto: Common evaluation methods of machine learning models verify the accuracy and expressiveness of the model, but not
 - whether there is **“too much data”** in the model
 - whether **irrelevant attributes** are considered in the model
 - whether model allows **conclusions about individual data sets/persons** from the training data
- Usually **no guarantee** and **no verification** about (absence of) personal data in the model

Machine learning models

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- **Simple models** may allow manual verification (or at least: plausibility checks) concerning the presence of personal data
- **Neural networks, deep learning**: Hard to understand even for experts; no intuitive way of checking for personal data

Machine learning models

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- Computer science research shows: This is, in many cases, incorrect
- Example: Shokri et al. 2017, “**Membership Inference** Attacks Against Machine Learning Models”
 - Common machine learning algorithms allow an attacker to conclude whether a specific data set (→ often: data about a specific person) was part of the training data or not
 - Finding has been confirmed in numerous other publications

Machine learning models

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- More privacy threats have been shown in different application scenarios (cmp. Al-Rubaie/Chang 2019)
 - **Private data in the clear** in case of outsourced computation
 - **Reconstruction attacks**: reconstruction of raw data from feature vectors
 - **Model inversion attacks**: reconstruction of feature vectors or raw data resembling the original training data – even if feature vectors are not part of the model

Countermeasures

- Privacy-preserving machine learning
 - Active research field
 - No definite “one size fits all” solution
- “Simplest” approach: Use **already anonymized** training data
 - **Independent** from actual machine learning algorithm
 - Might lead to **suboptimal** results
- Precise method to be used: Dependent on **application requirements**

Conclusion

- Training a machine learning model \neq anonymization
- Well-known result in the privacy research community
- Possibly less well-known result among practitioners
- Note: **GDPR** applies to processing of personal data
 - In computer science: Relatively short delay between research result and practical applicability
→ state of the art in research should be taken into account
- Countermeasures can be cumbersome and/or affect quality of results, but might be **legally required**

AI models are an abstraction which may or may not contain personal data. Data protection law needs to be taken into account.

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